

Time Scavengers, Inc.

Scavenging the fossil record for clues to Earth's climate and life

Facebook promotions keep people in the social media ecosystem, but do not encourage outside engagement

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Abstract

Social media provides an avenue to increase science literacy and engage individuals. Facebook is a compelling avenue for science communicators as it is widely used and features a broad audience. Here we use an existing project to evaluate the utility of Facebook promotional tools to engage users and drive traffic to the Time Scavengers website. Data were gathered from Facebook Insights, Ad Manager, and Google Analytics from May 2017 – October 2018. We employed two paid ads and three boosted posts as videos and images and examined engagement rate for each and determined the amount of traffic each promotion drove to the website. Results suggest that on average, Facebook boosted posts garner more engagement than paid advertisements. Overall, Facebook promotions do not significantly alter traffic to the website. We provide four evidence-based best practices that scientists or scientific organizations can follow when attempting to engage a community with educational, science-based content.

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Introduction

Advancing public science literacy is one of the more challenging tasks of the modern era. Whereas general scientific literacy is very high (Kennedy and Hefferon, 2019), it is sparse within specific topics, including climate change and evolutionary theory (Kennedy and Hefferon, 2019). These topics are consistently in the public sphere via the news media (Bolsen and Shapiro, 2018), through politics (e.g., Boykoff, 2008; Strauss, 2019), discussions of research breakthroughs and viral outbreaks (e.g., DeConto and Pollard, 2016; Fox, 2018), and extreme weather events (e.g., Whitmarsh, 2008; Mooney and Dennis, 2018). Yet, the majority of Americans trust scientists, not the media, as the most reliable source of information on climate change (Maibach et al., 2009, Nisbet and Scheufele, 2009). While some research has suggested that people with increased trust in scientific enterprise are more likely to accept scientific findings (Drummond and Fischhoff, 2017), some members of the public still do not deem climate change as a threat or do not understand the underlying principles that support the theory of evolution (Miller et al., 2006; Reynolds et al., 2010; Weber and Stern, 2011; Heddy and Nadelson, 2013). Science affects our everyday lives, thus it is imperative that science information be accessible, easily digestible, and meaningful to a public audience (Wibeck, 2014; Moser, 2010).

Time Scavengers is a science communication website that features blogs, informational pages, and teaching resources designed to engage the public in learning about climate change, evolution, paleontology, and geology (Lam et al., 2019). We used Time Scavengers's Facebook page as a single case study to explore if promotional tools can be used to drive traffic to the website, where users would potentially gain awareness and understanding of scientific topics, and engage with climate change and evolutionary theory information.

Facebook is a viable context for exploring engagement with climate change, as it is one of the most widely used social media platforms (Kennedy and Hefferon, 2019). Facebook was chosen as it (1) can reach broad audiences regardless of time and

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space, (2) provides an easy mechanism to create promotional content ('promotions') in the form of boosted posts (i.e. posts that were used to reach additional, non-page follower Facebook users; Table 1), and (3) advertisements can be easily constructed through Facebook's Ads Manager. This platform collects specific data associated with each promotion, which allowed us to determine and measure the success of each post. Using Time Scavengers's Facebook account as a basis for our single case study, our exploratory research questions are as follows: (1) Which promotional tools worked best for reaching and engaging Facebook users?; and (2) which type of content was most successful at driving traffic outside of the Facebook ecosystem to the Time Scavengers's website? Our goal was to determine if and what types of promotions are useful to increase traffic to the Time Scavengers's website.

Theoretical Grounding. To guide our case study, we use the lens of interest-based engagement, in which people are self-motivated and self-guided to participate in science practices (Azevedo, 2018). Social media provides an excellent frame for considering interest-based engagement, as users can engage with topics they are interested in as they interpret discourse, situations, and events based on their previous knowledge and experience (Zittoun and Brinkmann, 2012). Some science communicators have focused on the ways people measure behavioral engagement with public policy related to climate change (Feldman et al., 2015; Lubell et al., 2007; Roser-Renouf et al., 2014), such as through science cafes (Dallas, 2006; Dijkstra, 2017), science festivals (Sardo and Grand, 2016), and popup museums (Santos et al., 2018; Lundgren et al., 2020b). Such traditional methods offer the chance for people to interact with scientists and scientific topics in an accessible, face-to-face manner, but these events are somewhat limited in their reach. Our case study looks at how to increase the public's awareness, understanding, and engagement with climate change and evolutionary theory in the digital realm. To expand the reach of content and

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educational messaging, many organizations and scientists are turning to social media platforms including Twitter, Instagram, Snapchat, TikTok, and Facebook.

Previous Work using Facebook Promotions. Previous work has explored how various messaging strategies have been created to reach broader audiences on social media. For instance, Barnes et al. (2021) experimented with several methods, including boosted posts and advertisements, to recruit subjects for health studies. Meanwhile, Glasgow et al. (2018) used boosted posts to target specific users regarding public health messaging, finding that boosted posts were able to reach a wider audience. Additionally, some university libraries have explored using boosted posts to increase their campus visibility (Young et al., 2014; Chan, 2016). The research on boosted posts and paid advertisements comes from varied disciplines, yet in general, reaching broader audiences on Facebook can be accomplished through paid promotional tools. Herein, we seek to explore the use of Facebook promotional tools for broadening the reach of scientific content.

Other work has explicitly focused on how engagement rate is important when considering social media users as consumers as well as how engagement rates can be commodified for marketing purposes (Bitiktas and Tuna, 2020; Bonsón and Ratkai, 2013). Media type (video or image) has been explored in regard to how the content within messages affects engagement rate (e.g., Lai and To, 2015; Vitale, 2020).

Methods

Promotions. Facebook offers two tools for promotion: paid advertisements and boosted posts (Table 1, Figure 1). Advertisements have the ability to target specific audiences, and are created and scheduled through Facebook Ads Manager. Through Ads Manager, Facebook page administrators have the ability to target people from specific age groups, gender, and location. Advertisement campaigns can be subsampled and created within Ads Manager, meaning the same advertisement can have different

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targeted audiences to see how well each ad set performs across different targeted audiences. A limitation of advertisements is that they do not appear on Time Scavengers’s Facebook page timeline. However, advertisements can be shared among those who view it on their own timelines, groups, or pages. Boosted posts differ from advertisements, mainly in that they are not controlled or created through Facebook’s Ads Manager website. Boosted posts are regular posts that are made onto a page, but are then ‘boosted’ to a larger audience outside of a page’s normal following. They appear both on the Facebook page and in followers’ timelines. This function facilitates the ease of sharing the boosted post onto other pages and groups. Time Scavengers used both paid advertisements and boosted posts to determine which is more effective for encouraging learning and inquiry beyond the Facebook ecosystem to our educational website.

Table 1. Terms used in the text and their definitions and explanations regarding Facebook promotional tools.

Terms	Definition and Explanation
Post	Media (images or videos) along with text posted on the Time Scavengers Facebook page
Promotion	Advertisements or campaigns created through the Facebook platform that can be targeted to specific audiences. These include both boosted posts and paid advertisements.
Boosted Post	A post that was made to the Time Scavengers Facebook page and was then 'boosted' to reach a larger audience. Boosted posts are not created through the Facebook Ads Manager, and appear on people's Facebook pages who do not follow the page.
Paid Ad (or 'Ad')	A post that was created within the Facebook Ads Manager, where specific targeted audiences were selected. Paid ads appear on people's Facebook pages that may or may not be following the page.
Post Data	
Reach	The number of people who saw the boosted or paid ad on their Facebook page at least once.
Organic Reach	The number of people who saw the boosted posts without the paid promotional aspect.
Paid Reach	The number of people who saw the boosted post or paid ad because of the paid promotional aspect.
Views	The number of people who viewed videos associated with boosted posts or paid ads.
Impression	The number of times the boosted post or paid ad appeared on a screen.
Engagements	Interactions performed on the boosted post or paid ad, which includes likes, shares, comments, and clicking on the post.
Engagement Rate	A metric that indicates the performance of a boosted post or paid ad. Engagement rates are calculated as the total number of engagements divided by the total number of paid and organic reach for a post.

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	Paid Ad	Boosted Post
Appears on Facebook page	✓	✗
Location targeting	✓	✓
Age and gender targeting	✓	✓
Interest and behavior targeting	✓	✓
Language targeting	✗	✓
Multiple images	✗	✓
Instagram ads	✗	✓

Figure 1. The two promotional options (boosted posts and paid ads) on Facebook and the different capabilities available for each method.

Facebook Promotion Parameters. We employed two paid ads and three boosted posts (Table 2) with videos and images related to climate change and evolution between November 1, 2017 to October 17, 2018. As this exploratory research was conducted *a posteriori* of data collection, the promotion parameters were not uniform. In one instance, we took advantage of the ‘ad sets’ option within Facebook Ads Manager, which allows for a group of ads to run that share how, when, and where ads are shown but differ by their targeted audience. The two demographics that we targeted were people in the 18–65+ age range in states that voted Democratic and those that voted Republican in the 2016 election according to their electoral college results. This is because the Time Scavengers website was created to provide scientific information in a non-partisan context, and we wanted to investigate if targeting Democratic or Republican leaning states influenced post interactions. Election result data was taken from an election results archive website (National Archives, 2021) to determine which

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states fell into each category. The fifth promotion was a boosted post of a Time Scavengers blog which featured scientists describing their work. Each promotion ran between four and five days, and was intended to reach outside of the Time Scavengers's current followers. Four out of the five promotions were general information, meaning they provided a brief overview of the Time Scavengers site to attract potential new community members (Figure 2). The type of content varied between having an image or a short video clip (Table 2; Figure 2). The first boosted post was also shared into three active geoscience-related Facebook groups to help increase visibility: *Paleontology Education*, *Women in Paleontology* (now called *Equity in Paleontology*), and *Paleoceanography*. \$30 USD was used for each promotion period, regardless of promotion duration. For the ad set of Republican vs. Democratic states, we allocated \$30 per ad set, with a total promotional cost of \$60 (Table 2).

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Figure 2. Examples of Facebook boosted posts (A, B, D) and paid advertisement (C) on Facebook designed to attract more visitors to the Time Scavengers website. Each example employed a slightly different visual tactic to engage users. (A) promoted a general overview of the site. (B) was a 10-second slideshow that included images from various blog posts on Time Scavengers. (C) was a 10-second paid video ad that included the same images as (B). (D) was a blog post that was boosted.

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Table 2. Parameters input for each Facebook promotion.

Ad	Ad Type	Media	Amount Spent	Page Timeline	Shared	Demographics Targeted
November 3-7, 2017	Boosted Post	Static	\$30	Yes	Women in Paleontology, Paleocceanography, Paleontology Education	18-65+, grad school students
February 12-15, 2018	Boosted Post	Static	\$30	Yes	No	18-65+, grad school students, college grad, high school grad, in high school
May 1-4, 2018	Paid Ad	Video	\$30	No	No	18-65+, States that voted Democratic
	Paid Ad	Video	\$30	No	No	18-65+, States that voted Republican
July 17-21, 2018	Boosted Post	Video	\$60	Yes	No	18-65+, grad school students, college grad, high school grad, in high school
October 9-12, 2018	Paid Ad	Static	\$60	No	No	18-65+

Ad Hoc Exploratory Research. We examined the reach, engagements, and impressions on each of the promotions (Table 3). These data were extracted from the Facebook Ads Manager for paid ads and from Facebook Insights for the boosted posts (Table 2). For each promotion, post data (reach, impressions, and engagements; Table 1) were gathered for the lifetime of the post. Additional data from Facebook’s Ad Manager was also collated for each ad and boosted post, such as the number of women versus men and age groups of people who were interacting with the ads. For the boosted posts, Facebook separates out if reach and engagement were organic or facilitated through the paid promotion. To quantify how well our promotional ads performed in terms of reaching new users, we calculated engagement rate. This metric was defined following Bugeaud et al. (2016) and Lundgren et al. (2020) as:

$$\text{Engagement Rate} = [Total Engagements \div (Paid + Organic Reach)] \times 100$$

In this equation, data are normalized, as some posts had greater reach but fewer engagements, and vice versa. This metric is often reported to social media account administrators and represents the ratio between the number of likes, clicks, and shares on a post (engagements) and the organic and paid reach (number of people who saw

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the post) of the post (Bugeaud et al., 2016). Data on Time Scavengers website user traffic was collected via Google Analytics, including how people are finding Time Scavengers (e.g., social media, organic internet searches, and referrals). We then performed a t-test using GraphPad Prism version 9.4.1 for Mac t to compare the social media data to the Google Analytics data. We compared each promotional period to the Full Period to determine if promotions were altering traffic to the Time Scavengers website during these promotional periods.

Results

Table 3. Raw data for the promotional posts. 'Views' are only available for videos as it relates directly to how many times the video was viewed by individuals. 'Organic' indicates individuals that viewed the post without the aid of the paid promotion and 'paid' are the new views received directly from the paid promotion.

Promotion Information			Reach			Impressions		Engagements			
Ad Date	Type	Media	Views	Organic	Paid	Organic	Paid	Link Clicks	Likes	Shares	Rate
November 2017	Boosted Post	Image	-	4275	1556	8809	1646	0	163	29	3.29%
February 2018	Boosted Post	Image	-	653	2144	1293	2258	24	56	6	3.07%
May 2018	Paid Ad	Video	930	-	4993	-	5540	126	12	5	2.86%
July 2018	Boosted Post	Video	3296	776	3867	1191	3928	0	21	4	0.54%
October 2018	Paid Ad	Image	-	-	38,815	-	38,916	44	0	0	0.11%

Facebook Data. Combined, the three boosted posts reached a total of 7,567 people, whereas the two advertisements reached a total of 43,808 people (Paid Reach, Table 3). Calculating engagement rate removed the large variation in promotion reach and took user interactions with the content into account. The average engagement rate for paid ads was 1.49% versus 2.3% for the boosted posts. A boosted post with an image garnered the highest engagement rate (3.29%) and a paid advertisement with an image resulted in the lowest engagement rate (0.11%). The following two promotions had a <1% engagement rate with the October 2018 paid advertisement being anomalously low at 0.11% with almost no engagements. The video media includes 'views' as a metric

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of reach; the paid advertisement garnered 930 views whereas the boosted post accumulated 3,296 views, nearly three times as many.

The paid ad in May 2018 had additional parameters to target people ranging from 18–65+ and living in states that were Democratic or Republican in the 2016 elections based on the electoral college votes (Table 2). The results of this were combined in Table 3 and Figure 3 because the resulting values were nearly identical for both target groups. Among the boosted posts, the November post was shared by [authors] into three Facebook groups and had a total of zero link clicks, 163 reactions, and 29 shares (Table 3; Figure 3). The February boosted post was not shared into groups by the page admins and received more link clicks but less reactions and shares (Table 3; Figure 3). The July boosted post contained video media, which reached the largest paid audience of the boosted posts and garnered the least engagements (Table 3; Figure 3). The May paid ad garnered the most clicks of all of the promotions with fewer reactions and shares and a total reach of 4,993. The October paid ad reached more individuals than all of the other advertisements combined for a total reach of 38,815. This advertisement had the second highest amount of link clicks and no likes or shares (Table 3; Figure 3).

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Figure 3. Engagement rate for each of the promotions with clicks, reactions, and shares as percentages rather than raw counts (see Table 3). Promotional and content types are depicted as text at the top and icon respectively. The current industry standard (Bugeaud et al. 2018) and more recent average based on Lundgren et al. (2020) are depicted on the Engagement Rate axis.

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Website Visitor Data. Site visitor data were collected through Google Analytics for the entire duration of the promotional test period, November 1, 2017 to October 17, 2018. During this period, approximately two new blog posts were released and promoted on social media every week in an attempt to increase website traffic on a regular basis. The Facebook promotions were in addition to the regularly posted content. The increased site visitors during paid ads and boosted posts intervals correspond more closely to the release of new blog posts and Time Scavengers page shares, rather than the promotions themselves (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Number of visitors to the Time Scavengers website from November 1, 2017, 2018. Dashed vertical lines indicate periods within which paid ads and boosted posts ran. The bottom row of zoomed-in graphs increase resolution of site visitors, with the star symbol indicating when posts were shared on social media platforms within the run period for paid ads and boosted posts. Daily site user data is from Google Analytics.

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During promotion intervals, the number of new and returning visitors to the site was not significantly altered compared to the normal visitor data (Figure 5). Average returning users during boosted posts is 23.1% with 76.9% new individuals (Figure 5). This is higher than the total percentage of returning users for the year period at 19.7% and new users 80.3%. Comparatively, the paid ads have an average returning site visitor at 17.25% with 82.75% new visitors (Figure 5).

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Figure 5. Modes of acquisition and composition of site users for the full promotional test period (November 2017 to October 2018) compared to each of the promotion run periods. The type of promotion (boosted versus paid ad) and content (image versus video) are represented at the top of each run period. Data from Google Analytics.

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Using Google Analytics, we determined how users navigated to the Time Scavengers website: *Organic* (e.g., organic searches), *Social* (e.g., Facebook, Twitter, Reddit), *Direct* (e.g., bookmarks), or *Referral* (e.g., other sites). For the purposes of easier visualization of changes in Facebook traffic, we analyzed only the Facebook data from the combined Social category on Google Analytics. From November 1, 2017 to October 31, 2018 (Full Period on Figure 5) 63.4% of users came into the site via Organic, 14.9% Social, 14% Direct, and 7.7% Referral. During the first two promotions (November and February), both of which were boosted posts, the Social percentage increased to above 30%, a value twice that compared to the Full Period. For the study duration, Facebook drove 67.5% of the Social traffic to Time Scavengers’s website. During the first three promotions (November, February, and May) we saw an increase in traffic to the Time Scavengers website driven from Facebook, 77.33%, 73.33%, and 89.77% but these increases are not significant when compared to the full study period via a t-test (Table 4). The July and October promotions had less than the full study period at 60.47% and 46.53% respectively (Figure 5), which is also reflected in resulting p-values (Table 4).

Table 4. T-test for each promotional period as compared to the full time period.

Ad Date	Promotion Details	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degrees of Freedom	t-statistic	p value
Nov. 2017	Boosted, image	33.70	26.46	8	0.18	0.86
Feb. 2018	Boosted, image	32.98	23.41	8	0.24	0.82
May. 2018	Paid ad, video	35.44	33.68	8	0.08	0.94
Jul. 2018	Boosted, video	37.04	23.26	8	0.00	1.00
Oct. 2018	Paid ad, image	35.66	20.00	8	0.09	0.93

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The acquisition of site user data, specifically through Social channels, should also be made comparable in terms of promotional and media type (Table 5; Supplemental Material 1). This allows us to investigate the type of material that is most successful in driving traffic to our website. On average, boosted posts drove more individuals from Facebook to the website than the paid advertisements. Promotions with video media drove more individuals to the website than those with images (Table 5). Boosted posts and images had higher averages of new users than paid ads and videos (Table 5). The variation from the full study period is not significant for any of the promotional periods, regardless of type of promotion or media (Table 4).

Table 5. Average percent of users that came into the Time Scavengers website for the duration of the study period for better comparison of promotional type and media type. There were three boosted posts, three promotions with images, two paid ads, and two promotions with videos. Social (Other) includes Twitter, WordPress, Reddit, and more.

Route	Promotional Type		Media Type	
	Boosted	Paid Ad	Image	Video
Facebook	70.38	68.15	65.73	75.12
Social (Other)	29.62	31.85	34.27	24.88
Returning users	23.2	19.3	21.23	20.2
New Users	76.8	80.7	51.87	79.8

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Discussion

This case study investigated: (1) which promotional tool, paid advertisements or boosted posts, worked best for reaching and engaging Facebook users, and (2) if certain content paired with a promotional type was more successful at driving traffic from Facebook to the Time Scavengers website. Within Facebook, we found that boosted posts garnered the highest engagement rates, and our first paid advertisement garnered the highest overall engagement rates, with declining engagement throughout subsequent promotions. In addition, boosted posts were also slightly more successful than paid advertisements in driving traffic outside of Facebook to the Time Scavengers website.

Content Engagement within the Facebook Ecosystem. Our findings indicate that paid ads generally reached more people and boosted posts with images garnered the highest engagement rates. Over our study time period, we saw an increase in total reach and a decline in engagement rate regardless of promotion type. On average the boosted posts achieved a higher engagement rate than paid advertisements (2.3% and 1.49%, respectively). This result may indicate that boosted posts provide more affordances to the viewers, as boosted posts are inherently more interest-based as they first reach followers who are predisposed to engage with Time Scavenger content (Azevedo, 2018). Specifically, boosted posts provided a more specific call to action using tailored language (e.g., 'Read Kelly's post for more fun facts and engineering career advice!') that encouraged viewers to click the provided link in the post to read more about the boosted blog post on the website. On the other hand, paid advertisements included less calls to action, as these posts were more general and did not include language asking viewers to perform a specific action, such as click a link.

The initial boosted post with an image garnered the highest engagement rate of all promotional types. However, this higher engagement rate could have been the result of sharing the post into related Facebook groups, which increased reactions and views

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outside of the normal boosted material. The final image-based advertisement resulted in the lowest engagement rate but reached the most individuals. In this instance, we wanted to engage individuals rather than the promotion simply appearing on their timeline. The promotions, and our regularly posted content, were equally appealing to both men and women and had a relatively stable range of interested age groups. The promotional tools rapidly increased the amount of individuals that saw the post; however, the engagement rate peaked with our first promotion at 3.5%, which is lower than the current industry standard (Lundgren et al., 2020a). The type of media used in a promotion, either video or image, did not produce significant differences in engagement rate. Some work (e.g. Arcia, 2014; Vitale et al., 2019) has suggested that variation in image content leads to variable engagement rate. Our posts with images had engagement rates from 0.11–3.29%, which supports this previous work.

Highlighting, interpreting, and adding to the conversation on current industry standards for social media engagement rates is worthwhile. Industry standards for engagement rate are often internally conducted, and when they are reported, aggregated engagement rates are reported by industry (e.g. Bugeaud et al., 2016). The results of this study, which was from a Facebook page that sought to share information on climate change, evolution, and past life on Earth, does not necessarily fall into categories defined by industry or marketing. While one study (e.g. Lundgren et al., 2020a) described engagement rates for science-specific social media, the results of our study indicate that further research is necessary to delineate standard engagement rates for social media accounts that promote and share scientific content.

Monetary Return on Investment for Facebook Promotions. This study suggests that Facebook promotions have a diminishing return on investment through time, as our first promotion (boosted post) garnered an engagement rate of 3.29%, while our last promotion (paid ad) garnered an engagement rate of 0.11%. Previous Facebook ad campaigns (Young et al., 2014; Chan, 2016) targeted a narrow demographic in order to

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increase awareness and visibility of local libraries. Similar to our findings, Young et al. (2014) and Chan (2016) also found a decreasing number of interactions with their promotions from the start to end of their campaigns.

Regardless of diminishing return on investment, prior studies that used a conservative amount per advertisement campaign similar to our study, found that lower-budget promotions can still be effective to achieve the promotion's goals. For example, Glasgow et al. (2018) crafted a campaign to educate the public about mosquito-borne infections. Both Glasgow et al. (2018) and Chan (2016) indicated that with well-crafted campaigns, the appropriate audience can be reached with minimal ad costs.

Platt et al. (2016) used a larger budget of \$15,000 to create a public health Facebook advertising campaign lasting for 11 weeks, again targeting a certain demographic (Michigan residents aged 18–64 years old). Their campaign reached 1.88 million Facebook users, with differing engagement outcomes across ad sets varying by objective of the ad, content, budget, and duration of ads. The results of Platt et al. (2016) indicate that increased budgets for Facebook ads may be critical to reaching a much broader audience. This is not necessarily in contrast to our results and the findings of Chan (2016) and Glasgow et al. (2018) based on ads with relatively conservative prices, but does highlight the fact that an increased budget will exponentially reach more audience members, a finding that was also confirmed by Westerfield and Cain (2019).

Our final paid ad (October 2018) reached nearly forty thousand individuals but the engagement rate on the content was the lowest. This begs the question: is it enough to reach more individuals or should increasing engagement on the content be prioritized? At present, results from our study and others suggest that more financial investment should be made in the first ad or boosted post of the campaign, as there is a diminishing return on investment. This shared result indicates that more studies need to be conducted to better understand the parameters that may affect engagement with

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paid promotions on Facebook. Such factors may include time frame or season of the campaign, target audience, promotion tool, frequency and duration of ads, and fund amount.

Content that Promoted Leaving the Facebook Ecosystem. On average, boosted posts were slightly more effective at driving traffic to the Time Scavengers website. Similarly, promotions with videos were on average 10% better than images at driving traffic from Facebook to the website. If using Facebook promotional tools were an effective means of driving new people to the website, we would have expected to see an increased number of new users compared to the Full Period (see Figure 5). We see an increase in our returning users for two of the boosted posts and an increase in new users for the two paid ads. This makes sense as boosted posts appear in the Facebook timeline of our followers and therefore reach our established community whereas ads do not. These results show a ~5% variation between new and returning users throughout each of the promotional periods. This variation is not statistically significant when compared to the Full Period values. Many studies use Facebook to recruit survey participants (Arcia 2014; Choi et al. 2017; Forgasz et al. 2017) which is not totally dissimilar to our goal of directing traffic to a website. Most studies (e.g., Arcia 2014; Choi et al. 2017; Kayrouz et al. 2016) found variation in who clicked on an advertisement and who consented in the study but even with variation, which indicates that Facebook is still a valuable tool to access hard-to-reach populations.

Limitations and Future Directions. Time Scavengers promotional tools were initially used to increase community engagement outside of our personal circles, family, and colleagues, rather than as an explicit research project. As such, this case study did not employ a rigid framework when beginning to promote our content. This is why the first boosted post was a general overview of Time Scavengers, and was shared into other Facebook groups, whereas the second boosted post was a blog rather than a general

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informational post about Time Scavengers, like the first boosted post. Additionally, while paid advertisements from Facebook appear on Instagram as sponsored posts and in stories, we focused exclusively on the platform of Facebook. Future iterations of such studies could take advantage of the ease to post across Facebook and Instagram simultaneously, and determine if such promotional tools are useful in directing users outside of social media.

In addition to the above, we did not control for our promotions overlapping with newly released blogs and content on Time Scavengers's social media pages. Thus, there could be a bias in our data due to other posts released within the time frame of the five promotions. Future studies should implement a more rigid research framework that controls for such variables, perhaps by not releasing new content during the promotional periods. Relatedly, an investigation into how engagement rates for promotional content created by science communication/education Facebook pages are affected by the time of day or days of the week would be a useful contribution to the literature. There has been nascent work on this for other platforms (i.e., Instagram) and for organic content, yet it remains underexplored for Facebook (Authors et al., 2021).

The largest unknown in our case study is how Facebook algorithms change, and how such changes may influence our data and who sees paid ads and boosted posts. As Facebook's algorithm is continually being updated, and how it changes is not transparent, it is nearly impossible to tell what effect this has on longer-term case studies and research studies conducted on the platform.

One of the more unexpected findings from this case study was the diminishing return on investment through time, which was a finding surfaced in the studies by Young et al. (2014) and Chan (2016). This finding could be explored within a more rigid framework, as diminishing returns on investment could impact how businesses and other groups conduct advertisements on social media platforms.

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Conclusion

In this case study, we described how we created a series of promotional events for a science communication Facebook page and the outcomes of such promotional events. We provide evidence of promising practices that other outreach professionals may wish to use and study in greater depth including aspects of low budget Facebook marketing. Small advertising budgets can help organizations engage different audiences on Facebook as well as drive small amounts of traffic to organizational websites. It is important to note that low budget marketing on Facebook is useful; health-based organizations have found that recruiting hard-to-reach populations can be accomplished via Facebook advertising and our findings agree.

Much of Time Scavengers's website traffic is based on Organic Google queries rather than directed from social media platforms; 80 percent of Time Scavengers website traffic was not derived from social media. This could indicate that site content, keywords, and phrases picked up from search engines are more important for reaching new individuals interested in climate and evolutionary sciences than using paid promotional tools on Facebook. However, we showed that there was increased traffic to the website from Facebook during the promotional periods; the extent of increased traffic was more limited than expected considering engagement rates with boosted posts. Thus, the idea of driving traffic to a project website through Facebook can work, although it seems that users are engaging with the content but not leaving the Facebook ecosystem.

We suggest four evidence-based best practices that scientists or scientific organizations can follow when attempting to engage a community with educational, science-based content: (1) use paid ads to rapidly reach a large audience; (2) boost posts to increase engagement among users with shared interests on Facebook; (3) intentionally promote to audiences via the use of Facebook's target audience tool to increase impact; and (4) be strategic about budgeting as there appears to be a rate of diminishing returns in the long-term.

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Supplemental Material

Supplemental Material 1: Raw user acquisition data as percents that correspond to Figure 5 and the averages represented in Table 5 of the promotional and media type for each of the modes of acquisition.

Date	Type	Media	New Users	Returning Users
Full Period	-	-	19.6	80.4
Nov. 2017	Boosted	Image	24.8	75.2
Feb. 2018	Boosted	Image	19.3	80.7
May. 2018	Paid Ad	Video	15.2	84.8
Jul. 2018	Boosted	Video	25.2	74.8
Oct. 2018	Paid Ad	Image	19.3	80.7

Date	Organic	Social (Other)	Facebook	Direct	Referral
Full Period	63.4	32.5	67.5	14	7.7
Nov. 2017	49.6	77.33	22.66	14.3	4.6
Feb. 2018	43	73.33	26.67	10.7	11.2
May. 2018	59.9	89.77	10.23	13.7	3.6
Jul. 2018	63.8	60.47	39.53	15.5	5.9
Oct. 2018	54.2	46.53	53.47	19.3	4.8

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